

Study of Nerve Conduction in Non-Diabetic Offspring of Type 2 Diabetic Parents of Students in NMCH, Patna

Ravish Kumar Sinha¹, Mrs. Rita Kumari²

¹Tutor, Department of Physiology, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor & HOD, Department Of Physiology, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 10-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ravish Kumar Sinha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Diabetes is a major contributor to global morbidity and mortality. Genetic factors play a significant role in the development of the disease, and various gene polymorphisms and mutations may influence its clinical presentation. Recent studies on the genetic components of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) have demonstrated that early indications of altered brain and autonomic systems are present in even non-diabetic children of diabetic parents.

Objectives: The objective is to examine the median motor nerve conduction parameters in non-diabetic offspring of parents with T2DM compared to those with non-diabetic parents, and to analyze any differences between these groups.

Methods: On the hands of sixty healthy individuals between the ages of eighteen and twenty-five, a nerve conduction investigation of the motor component of the median nerve was carried out. All of the study's participants had normal BMIs and were divided equally into two groups: 30 children of parents with T2DM and 30 children of parents without the disease.

Results: The motor component of the median nerve's latency, amplitude, and conduction velocity did not significantly change between the two groups.

Conclusion: There were no discernible variations in motor nerve latencies between the groups according to the study. This is in contrast to results from earlier research in comparable populations that showed altered visually evoked potentials and autonomic dysfunction. The lack of engagement of the somatic nerve may be explained by the glycation of neural structures, which may have an impact on neuronal activity.

Keywords: Motor Nerve Conduction, Children of Type 2 Diabetic Parents.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Diabetes has a greater impact on Asian and American Indian populations compared to other groups. It is a significant contributor to illness and disease globally [1]. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is an inherited metabolic condition that affects the regulation of glucose levels in the body. It can lead to complications in both small blood vessels (microvascular) and large blood vessels (macrovascular). These complications can result in stroke, kidney failure, blindness, heart attack, and the need for lower limb amputation. Diabetes was a factor in 1.6 million fatalities in 2015, according to WHO surveys, and it is predicted that diabetes would rank seventh in terms of causes of death by 2030 [2]. Studies have found that people with a positive family history are more likely to develop T2DM. This suggests that, similar to other inherited disorders, T2DM is a genetic endowment that is passed down through the generations, with the condition's expression becoming more noticeable with each passing generation [4, 5].

T2DM, a polygenic condition, is caused by a combination of genes, environment, and other factors. Latest medical investigations have revealed controversial discoveries about the cause of diabetes in genetically susceptible populations. These studies suggest that even with their normal blood sugar levels, non-diabetic children of diabetic parents may have different overall bodily functioning. The neurophysiological study of this vulnerable population has revealed changes in autonomic functioning and extended delays in the visual evoked potential (VEP), signifying possible involvement of the autonomic nervous system and poor visual processing, even in the absence of diabetes [6,7]. According to biochemical and molecular studies conducted in similar populations, the children of parents with diabetes who do not have diabetes themselves also show signs of microalbuminuria, increased production of the oxidative stress marker 8-hydroxydeoxy-guanosine (8-OHdG), and impaired endothelium dependent

vasodilation [7-9]. These findings suggest that the changes observed in offspring of parents with diabetes may not be directly linked to the inadequate control of blood sugar levels, which is known to cause complications in the small and large blood vessels. This study aimed to assess alterations in nerve conduction parameters due to neuropathy, a significant complication of diabetes micro vasculopathies. Additionally, it observed retinopathic, autonomic dysfunction, and nephropathic features in the non-diabetic state of euglycemic offspring with diabetic parents. The research findings indicate that the involvement of large myelinated fibres is the sole factor responsible for the alteration in sensory action potential. Additionally, the deceleration of motor nerve conduction speed in both the upper and lower limbs exhibits similarity [10, 11]. This study was conducted to assess any alterations in the motor nerve conduction (MNC) of the median nerve in individuals who do not have diabetes but have parents with diabetes.

Objectives

To determine any alterations in nerve conduction among non-diabetic children of diabetic parents, the following objectives are essential:

1. To evaluate the conduction velocity, amplitude, and motor distal latencies of the median nerve in the control and study groups.
2. To analyze the differences in MNC parameters within the study group and compare these results with those of the control group.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Physiology at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, following approval from the institutional ethics committee. A total of 86 volunteers were initially recruited, with 60 participants ultimately included in the study. The participants were right-handed young adults, evenly allotted into two groups: 30 in the study group and 30 in the control group, with equal gender distribution in each group. Female participants were asked to undergo assessments during the menstrual phase to account for the influence of ovarian hormones on neural function during the follicular and luteal phases.

Study Groups: The study group consisted of non-diabetic volunteers with a family history of T2DM (30 participants: 15 males and 15 females),

matched with the control group for age and BMI. The control group included non-diabetic volunteers without a family history of T2DM (30 participants: 15 males and 15 females), also matched for age and BMI.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants were healthy, non-obese individuals with a BMI ranging from 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m² and aged between 18-23 years.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals with upper limb weakness, tingling, pain, numbness, chronic diseases (such as diabetes mellitus, thyroid disease, liver disease, or hypertension), those who were smokers, alcoholics, athletes, or had a parental history of hypertension were excluded from the study.

Methodology: The selection of participants was based on the study's specific criteria for inclusion and exclusion. The technique was thoroughly elucidated, and written informed consent was acquired from all participants. Anthropometric data, specifically height and weight, were collected in order to compute the BMI. Bilateral MNC studies of the median nerve were performed in the research laboratory using NEUROSTIM, MEDICAID SYSTEMS, and surface electrodes. The recording electrode was put in close proximity to the motor point of the Abductor Pollicis Brevis muscle, whereas the reference electrode was positioned 3 cm away from the active electrode at the first metacarpophalangeal joint. An intermediary ground electrode was positioned between the stimulating and recording electrodes. Initially, supramaximal stimulation was administered at the wrist and subsequently at the elbow using stimulating electrodes in order to measure the Compound Muscle Action Potential (CMAP). The measurement was taken of the distance between the wrist and elbow. The Motor Distal Latency (MDL), Amplitude (Amp), and Conduction Velocity (CV) were measured and documented. The operation was conducted at an ambient room temperature of 23°C to 25°C in order to minimise the impact of temperature on nerve conduction.

Statistical Analysis: The mean plus or minus standard deviation was shown. The study used SPSS 17. Unpaired Student's t-tests were used to compare parameters between groups, with a P value of 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Observation and results

Table 1: Comparison of Study and Control Group Anthropometric Measurements

Parameters	Study Group	Control Group	P Value
No. of participants	30	30	-
Male/Female	15/15	15/15	-
Age (in years)	18.17 ± 1.15	18.29 ± 0.8	0.932
BMI (Kg/m ²)	20.15 ± 1.4	21.37 ± 1.23	0.5153

There were no substantial variations in age or BMI between the study and control groups, and both groups had an equal gender distribution.

Table 2: Comparison of the Median MNC Parameters in the Study and Control Groups' Right (Dominant) Hands

MNC Parameters	Study Group	Control Group	P Value
Latency (ms)	3.13 ± 0.81	2.59 ± 1.4	0.0726
Amplitude (mV)	8.94 ± 1.29	9.58 ± 1.42	0.0728
Conduction Velocity (m/s)	56.19 ± 2.34	57.51 ± 3.08	0.0667

A comparison of the motor component of the right median nerve's latency, amplitude, and conduction velocity between the study and control groups is shown in the accompanying table. The results

reveal that there are no statistically significant changes in any of the parameters, as evidenced by P values greater than 0.05.

Table 3: Comparison of the Median MNC Parameters in the Study and Control Groups' Left (Non-Dominant) Hands

MNC Parameters	Study Group	Control Group	P-Value
Latency (ms)	3.69 ± 1.21	2.98 ± 1.79	0.0771
Amplitude (mV)	7.26 ± 2.39	8.24 ± 1.95	0.0871
Conduction Velocity (m/s)	57.62 ± 1.76	58.49 ± 2.07	0.0847

The motor component of the left median nerve's latency, amplitude, and conduction velocity are compared between the study and control groups in the accompanying table. Just with the results for the right hand, there were no notable variations in any of the parameters, since all P values were greater than 0.05.

Discussion

T2DM refers to a collection of metabolic illnesses that are marked by disrupted regulation of glucose levels in the body. This disruption is caused by impairments in the secretion and/or function of insulin. Untreated hyperglycemia can lead to dysfunction, chronic damage, and failure in various organs, such as the heart, kidneys, blood vessels, eyes, and nerves [12]. The mesangial cells in the renal glomerulus, the neurones and Schwann cells in the peripheral nerves, and the capillary endothelial cells in the retina are especially susceptible to diabetic complications because they cannot effectively control the entry of glucose in a high blood sugar environment and maintain a consistent level of glucose inside the cells, unlike other tissues in the body [13].

Chronic hyperglycemia is the cause of diabetic outcomes because it dysregulates glucose entry into vulnerable tissues, which reduces antioxidants through the polyol pathway, compromises endothelial functions by altering intracellular proteins, and modifies the extracellular matrix by forming and diffusing advanced glycation end products (AGE products) out of these cells. Additionally, it causes cellular derangement by activating the protein kinase C pathway, which upregulates the production of vasoconstrictors and downregulators, and increases the expression of transforming growth factor-1 and plasminogen

activator inhibitor-1 due to the enhanced hexosamine pathway activity. All of these processes eventually result in microangiopathy, which impairs the ability of delicate tissues to operate [13]. Therefore, hyperglycemia is essentially secondary to the mechanism of diabetes complications. However, controversial findings of altered organ functions, such as markedly increased albumin excretion, elevated levels of oxidative stress markers in serum, impaired sympathovagal balance, and prolonged VEP latencies in the offspring of diabetic parents who are normoglycemic (not diabetic) have recently been reported in medical literature.

These notable observations challenge the idea that hyperglycemia is the initial cause of systemic dysfunction and impaired control of blood sugar levels, which then leads to damage in the nerves, retina, and kidney functions. These observations highlight the presence of systemic dysfunction in individuals who do not have diabetes but have parents with diabetes and are genetically prone to developing the condition. Thus, it is conceivable that mechanisms other than hyperglycemia deteriorating systemic processes ought to be involved in such circumstances. The role of epigenetic modification of the diabetes phenotype's manifestation is a likely mechanism.

It has been shown that retinopathy is more significant in diabetics with neuropathy [14]. Given that non-diabetic children of diabetic parents have been found to exhibit decreased activity throughout the visual pathway, this study aims to evaluate any potential changes in nerve conduction in a comparable cohort. Neural conduction investigations can be used to identify nerve injury and associated derangement.

Studies on the conduction of motor neurones examine particular factors such as conduction velocity, amplitude, and latency. The compound muscle action potential (CMAP) latency measures the speed at which nerves conduct, whereas the CMAP amplitude measures the density of nerve fibres. The motor nerve stimulates the muscle mass, which causes it to contract [15].

As previously stated, long-term high blood sugar levels result in the creation and accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGE) in the connective tissue collagens, nerve fibre axoplasm, Schwann cells, and endoneurial vessels. This, in turn, leads to a slowing of nerve conduction velocity, a decrease in nerve sodium levels, a decrease in K-ATPase activity, and a reduction in the size of myelinated nerve fibres [16].

Conversely, it has also been noted that neuropathy in diabetics is associated with a mutation in the Na,K-ATPase gene, highlighting the importance of genes in disease amplification [17]. Since T2DM is a polygenic disorder involving over 100 gene loci, the expression of certain genes determines when the condition begins and progresses, resulting in the development of the diabetic phenotype [18]. Consequently, the epigenetic mechanism of interaction between these diabetes genes with other regulatory genes and the environment may account for the observation of altered activities even in the euglycemic condition of non-diabetic children of diabetic parents.

This study was designed to estimate the nerve conduction parameters of the motor component of the median nerve in asymptomatic diabetics with subclinical neuropathy. It is known that the involvement of the motor component of the median nerve can occur even before the onset of clinical neuropathy. This is why the motor component of the median nerve was chosen for assessment, as it can be easily accessed [19]. In our pilot investigation, we did not see any noticeable changes in motor nerve conduction. This lack of alteration could be attributed to the fact that the neural system was not affected due to the participants' non-diabetic condition. [20] It is advisable to reach this conclusion only after evaluating the motor and sensory nerves in both the upper and lower limbs, as similar populations have shown changes in VEP, which are indicative of neural involvement.

Conclusion

Although altered autonomic functions and alterations in VEP have been documented in a comparable group, in our pilot investigation we detected no significant change in the nerve conduction velocity of the motor component of the median nerve among the non-diabetic kids of diabetic parents. The findings of our investigation

support the theory that the brain's involvement is incidental to the production and accumulation of advanced glycation end products brought on by hyperglycemia. Since the study population consisted of individuals who are not diabetics but are genetically predisposed to the disease, the reason for the lack of variation in the nerve conduction parameters might be that their glycaemic regulation was unimpaired. Nevertheless, confirmation of the theory that no brain function is involved in them would need a thorough assessment of the motor and sensory components of every peripheral nerve. Future studies will therefore focus on testing this idea since it is necessary to build a large population study and take into account the correlation between the parental contribution and inheritance.

References

1. Wy So, Mcy Ng, Sc Lee, T. Sanke, H. K. Lee, J.C.N Chan. Genetics of type 2 diabetes mellitus. HKMKJ. 2000. 6:69-76.
2. World Health Organization. Diabetes, Factsheet Internet Geneva: World Health Organization. 2017. November. Available from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs312/en/>.
3. Klein BE, Klein R, Moss SE, Cruickshanks KJ. Parental history of diabetes in a population based study. Diabetes Care. 1996; 19 (8): 827-30.
4. Marianne AB van der Sande, Gijs EL Walraven, Paul JM Milligan, Winston AS Banya, Sana M Ceesay, Ousman A Nyan, Keith PWJ McAdam. Family history: an opportunity for early interventions and improved control of hypertension, obesity and diabetes. Bulletin of the World Health Organization, 2001.79(4): 321-8.
5. Anitha Achuthan, Janani Ramesh. Pattern Visual Evoked Potential in Non-Diabetic offsprings of Type II Diabetes. JMR 20 15;1(3):83-86.
6. Khatri Anshu, Aggarwal Tanu, Changotra Parshant. Heart Rate Variability In Non Diabetic Offsprings Of Type 2 Diabetic Patients. Journal of Advance Researches in Biological Sciences, 2013, Vol. 5 (2). P. 139-43.
7. Goldfine AB, Beckman JA, Betensky RA, Devlin H, Hurley S, Varo N et al. Family history of diabetes is a major determinant of endothelial function. Journal of the American College of Cardiology. 2006. June 20;47(12):2456-61.
8. Gruden G, Cavallo-Perin P, Olivetti C, Repetti E, Sivieri R, Bruno A, Pagano G. Albumin excretion rate levels in non-diabetic offspring of NIDDM patients with and without

- nephropathy. *Diabetologia*. 1995. Oct 1;38(10):1218-22.
9. Hasan M, Mohieldein AH, Almutairi FR. Comparative study of serum 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine levels among healthy offspring of diabetic and non-diabetic parents. *International Journal of Health Sciences*. 2017. Jul;11(3):33.
 10. Refaat R, Abdelhameed AM, Elbarbary NS, El-Hilaly RA. Evaluation of median nerve in children with type1 diabetes using ultrasonographic imaging and electrophysiology. *The Egyptian Journal of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine*. 2013. September 30;44(3):563-72.
 11. Said G. Diabetic neuropathy-a review. *Nature clinical practice Neurology*. 2007. June 1;3(6):331-40.
 12. American Diabetes Association. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care*. 2004 Jan 1;27 (suppl 1). S.5-10.
 13. Chakdoufi, S., Moumen, A., & Guerboub, A. Dyslipidemia and Diabetic Retinopathy in Moroccans Type 2 Diabetics Patients: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Jour Med Resh and Health Sci*, 2023;6(3):2471–2479. <https://doi.org/10.52845/Jmrhs/2023-6-3-1>
 14. Brownlee M. The pathobiology of diabetic complications. *Diabetes*. 2005 June 1;54(6):1615-25.
 15. Sharma VK, Joshi MV, Vishnoi AA. Interrelation of retinopathy with peripheral neuropathy in diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Clinical Ophthalmology and Research*. 2016. May 1;4(2):83.
 16. Daube JR, Rubin DI. Nerve conduction studies. //Aminoff's *Electrodiagnosis in Clinical Neurology*. 6th ed. China: Elsevier Saunders Inc., 2012: 2906.
 17. Sugimoto K, Yasujima M, Yagihashi S. Role of advanced glycation end products in diabetic neuropathy. *Current pharmaceutical design*. 2008. April 1;14(10):953-61.
 18. Vague P, Dufayet D, Coste T, Moriscot C, Jannot MF, Raccah D. Association of diabetic neuropathy with Na/K ATPase gene polymorphism. *Diabetologia*. 1997. April 1; 40(5):506-11.
 19. Gaulton KJ. Mechanisms of type 2 diabetes risk loci. *Current diabetes reports*. 2017. Sep 1; 17(9):72.
 20. Garg R, Kumar A, Dhar U. A Study of Median Nerve Conduction Velocity in Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 in Neurologically Asymptomatic Patients. *International Journal of Health Science and Research*. 2013; 3(5):42-9.